

Estimation of *p*-Benzoquinone with Iron(II), Vanadium(II), Vanadium(III) and the Determination of Iron(II) and Vanadium(III)

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p-Benzoquinone can be estimated with iron(II) in buffer solutions in presence of oxalate and in phosphoric acid medium potentiometrically and visually using cacotheline, methylene blue and thionine as indicators. Vanadium(II) and vanadium(III) are used for the estimation of *p*-Benzoquinone in acetic acid medium potentiometrically and visually using the above indicators. Finally *p*-Benzoquinone is used for the potentiometric determination of iron(II) and vanadium(III) in phosphoric acid and acetic acid media respectively and iron(II) can be determined in phosphoric acid medium visually using the above indicators.

P-BENZOQUINONE was determined by Headridge and Wilson¹ potentiometrically at pH 3.0 in presence of hydrofluoric acid and ammonium fluoride. Tsung-Chi Tso and Peng-Ling Chu² used electrogenerated quinone for the coulometric titration of titanium(III) and vanadium(II). So far the reaction between *p*-Benzoquinone and vanadium(III) is not studied. Also in view of the hazards involved to the glassware while handling hydrofluoric acid and ammonium fluoride, the reaction between quinone and iron in buffer solutions is studied in the presence of other non-harmful complexing agents for iron(III) and also the study is extended for the determination of quinone with iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium. In this paper the details of the estimation of quinone with vanadium(II) and vanadium(III) both by potentiometric and visual methods are also presented along with the details for the determination of vanadium(III) with quinone through a potentiometric end-point.

Experimental

Reagents :

p-Benzoquinone solution : About 0.03*M* solution of *p*-Benzoquinone is prepared and standardised iodometrically³. Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate : 0.1*M* solution is prepared in 0.25*M* H₂SO₄ and standardised with standard potassium dichromate.

Vanadium(II) Sulphate solution : 0.05*M* vanadium(II) sulphate solution is prepared according to the method of Matrka et al⁴ and standardised⁵.

Vanadium(III) Sulphate solution: 0.1*M* vanadium(III) sulphate solution is prepared by electrolytic reduction of 0.1*N* sodium vanadate in 0.25*M* H₂SO₄ and standardised according to the method of Rao and Rao⁶.

Indicators : 0.2% cacotheline⁷, 0.1% methylene blue and 0.1% thionine solutions are prepared.

Syrupy phosphoric acid (pro-analysi, E. Merck) and glacial acetic acid (Analar, BDH) are employed.

All the other reagents are of analytical reagent grade quality.

Apparatus : The potentiometric assembly and the titration vessel is just the same as given in our previous publication⁸ except the potentiometer used here is of the Junior Cambridge potentiometer (W.G. Pye & Co.).

Recommended Procedure : An aliquot volume of quinone, Walpole buffer (pH. 3.05) and required volume of 0.2*M* oxalate (0.03*M* overall oxalate concentration) or required volume of phosphoric acid to give 8*M* (while iron(II) is used as titrant) or required volume of glacial acetic acid to give 6*M* (while vanadium(II) and vanadium(III) are used as titrants) are taken in the titration vessel described and diluted to 40 ml. Carbon dioxide is passed through the contents for 10 minutes. Then the contents are titrated with reductant solution noting down the potentials after the addition of each aliquot of the titrant. The potential breaks per 0.04ml. titrant and the range of determination carried out in each case are :— iron(II)-175 mV, 3-30 mg. (buffer solutions); 150mV, 3-23mg (phosphoric acid); vanadium(II)-120mV, 4-39 mg. and vanadium(III)-100mV, 4-39mg.

Similarly iron(II) and vanadium(III) were determined potentiometrically by taking the test solution into the titration vessel after passing carbon dioxide for 10 minutes and titrating with quinone. The potential break at the equivalence point per 0.04ml. of quinone and the range of determination carried out in each case are :— iron(II)-120mV, 2-15mg; and vanadium(III)-90mV, 2-17mg. Stable potentials were immediately obtained throughout the titration in all the above cases.

Also *p*-Benzoquinone can be determined visually with iron(II) in pH 4.98 in presence of 0.03*M* sodium oxalate using 0.3ml. of cacotheline (7-21mg) or 0.05ml. of thionine (6-15.50mg) or in 10*M* phosphoric acid medium using 0.3ml. of cacotheline (14-25mg) or 0.05ml. of methylene blue (6-20mg) or 0.05ml. of thionine (7-18mg) and with vanadium(II) in 6*M* acetic acid medium using 0.3ml. of cacotheline (4-37mg.) or 0.05ml. of methylene blue (6.5-39.0mg) or 0.05ml. of thionine (3-27.5mg) and finally with vanadium(III) in 8*M* acetic acid medium using 0.3ml. of cacotheline (6.5-39.0mg) or 0.05ml. of thionine (6-29.0mg).

Just as in potentiometric method iron(II) can be determined with *p*-Benzoquinone in 10*M* phosphoric acid medium using cacotheline, methylene blue or thionine as indicator in the range of 4-15mg.

Discussion

The advantage of the present method for the determination of quinone with iron(II) in buffer solutions over the past method¹ is that the chemicals involved in this method are not hazardous as those in method¹. The advantage of the use of phosphoric acid medium for the determination of quinone with iron(II) as compared within buffer solutions is that quinone can be used for the determination of iron(II) which is not possible in the latter case.

In the determination of vanadium (III) with quinone arsenic(III), vanadium(IV), uranium(IV), molybdenum(V), antimony(III), nickel(II), cobalt(II),

zinc(II), manganese(II), barium(II), magnesium(II), bromide, sulphate, citrate, oxalate and tartrate chloride, do not interfere. The main advantage of the present method is that vanadium(III) can be determined in presence of iron(II) which is not possible with other oxidising agents.

In the determination of iron(II) with quinone all the above listed cations and anions do not interfere except vanadium(IV).

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References

1. J. B. HEADRIDGE and JEFFERY WILSON, *Analyst.*, 1970, 95, 164.
2. TSUNG-CHI TSO and PENG-LING CHU., *Hua Hsueh Hsueh Pao.*, 1965, 31, 299.
3. A. VALEUR., *Compt. Rend.*, 1899, 129, 552.
4. M. MATRKA and Z. SAGNER, *Chem. Listy*, 1957, 51, 68.
5. C. M. ELLIS and A. I. VOGEL, *Analyst.*, 1956, 81, 693.
6. G. GOPALA RAO and P. KANTA RAO., *Talanta*, 1966, 13, 1335.
7. G. GOPALA RAO, N. KRISHNA MURTY and V. NARAYANA RAO., *Talanta*, 1965, 12, 243.
8. N. KRISHNA MURTY and V. SATYANARAYANA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 712.